

Implication of Plato's Allegory of the Cave in the present day Modern Political Order

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Abstract- Plato the great philosopher of all the times has given us an incredible Allegory. This Allegory is named by him as the Allegory of the cave because he uses the backdrop of the cave to explain, how the reality is different from that what it appears to be. He demonstrates how intellectual enlightenment plays a great role in getting liberated and also helping others liberate from the bondages of ignorance along with the physical, mental and political imprisonment in which they were living happily. This Allegory of the cave primarily has epistemological and metaphysical nature however the researcher in this study has made an attempt of understanding the allegory and interpret it in political sense by applying it to the present day political order. This paper also tries to analyze the important role of education in good governance and the role of Plato's philosopher that is the politicians in the present day in the process of liberating the ignorant masses with the aid of higher education from the social and political shackles.

Key Words - Allegory, Cave, Education, Escape, Governance, Politician, Prisoner, Shackles.

Rationale of the Study

Plato in his Allegory of the Cave has explained the importance of education for the purpose of good governance. He said that the philosopher king must be well educated and only then he can enlighten the ignorant masses by establishing an ideal state with a perfect frame work of good governance. In the present day modern democratic political order, each and every profession needs some basic educational qualification however the politicians who become the legislatives or the executives do not need any specific higher educational qualification. Plato insists that in democracy the ignorant masses elect the uneducated leaders and this leads to their final ruin and thus democracy is not a suitable form of Government. Researcher in this research paper has tried to analyze Plato's theory of Allegory of the Cave and has tried to establish the nexus between importance of educated politicians for good governance.

Objective of the Study

The following are the objectives of the research-

1. To analyze Plato's theory of The Allegory of the Caves.
2. To analyze the significance of education explained by Plato in the allegory.
3. To construct a relation between education and good governance.
4. To prove that education is importance for good governance.
5. To establish that the present day politicians should be educated just like Plato's philosopher king.

Hypothesis

Education is an important qualification for the politicians in our present day modern political order.

Methodology

For the purpose of analyzing Implication of Plato's Allegory of the Cave in the present day Modern Political Order, the researcher had adopted the descriptive and analytical research methodologies. The researcher extensively collected secondary data and has analyzed the same in order to prove the hypothesis and to reach to the conclusion and as well as be able to give the appropriate suggestions.

Introduction

The history of political science reveals clearly that many political thinkers have contributed to it extensively. Amongst all the political philosophers Plato is probably the greatest philosopher of all the ages. Plato is the Athenian philosopher who initiated the Academy for higher learning and for spreading the importance of education. He himself was the student and a good friend of the greatest political philosopher, Socrates. Socrates has been credited for using dialogue as a method of discovering the truth. He in spite of being a great philosopher himself, did not write any of his own theories. All that we know about Socrates' philosophy is through Plato's work. Plato wrote down Socrates' philosophies in the dialogue form after he was sentenced to death by the Athenian democrats. Therefore, we can clearly see strong reflection of Socrates' thoughts in Plato's work. The Allegory of the Cave also which is Plato's one of the several other great philosophical works is attributed to Socrates. Socrates had narrated this Allegory to Plato's brother Glaucon and Plato had written it down in form of a dialogue between the two. We can find the Allegory of the Cave in chapter VII of Plato's classic work The Republic, written around B.C.E. 375. The republic is considered as Plato's best work. It is the most important and

apparently the 1st book on government, state and many more other important aspects dealing with political science. Plato in *The Republic* elaborates on how, in order to explain the true notion of justice a group decides to create an ideal imaginary city state. He insisted to build the ideal city state on three pillars, such as of justice, virtue and happiness. The city state was to be governed by the philosopher king, who was a well-educated person coming from an aristocratic family. The people living in the just city state were classified by Plato into three different categories such as firstly the Ruler who had the virtue of knowledge by which he could understand what is right and wrong. Secondly the Guardians who had the virtue of courage and by using it they could protect the city and take care of the people. Finally, the producers whom he calls as the artisans who had the virtue of appetite and so by using such a virtue they would provide goods and service for the people in the city state.

Plato has divided *The Republic* in a series of ten books. Each book covers a different aspect of his philosophy. The book VII covers *The Allegory of the Cave* in which Socrates explains the importance of education as the means by which the human soul is directed away from the basic human desires. Plato through the dialogues of Socrates further elaborately explains and proves that education is the most important ingredient required for a politically perfect state. He explains how good quality education can create great leaders in the form of the philosopher king. He further demonstrates how intellectual enlightenment plays a great role in getting liberated and also helping others liberate from the bondages of ignorance along with the physical, mental and political imprisonment in which they were living happily. He explains how educated philosopher king can establish an ideal city state by good governance. In this paper the researcher intends to understand and analyze Plato's *Allegory of the Cave* and interpret its underpinnings to the present day political order in India.

'The Allegory of the Cave' - As it is

In the *Allegory of the Cave*, Plato segregates the people who mistakes sensory knowledge for the truth and the people who really do see the truth. For explaining this Plato asked us to Imagine a cave, which had three prisoners in it since their birth. They had never seen outside of the cave so did not know what was outside the cave. The prisoners were tied in one place to some rocks to prevent them from escaping from the cave, in order to prevent them

from looking at anything but the stonewall in front of them, their arms and legs were shackled and their heads were also tied. Behind the prisoners was a fire, and in between the prisoners and the fire was a raised walkway. People outside the cave carrying things such as animals, plants, food and stones would walk along this walkway Now the prisoners cannot look at anything behind or to the sides because they were shackled and constantly had to look at the wall in front of them. When people walk along the walkway, the prisoners can see only the shadows cast on to the wall of the objects which the people were carrying on their heads. As the prisoners had never seen the real objects ever before, they would believe that the shadows of objects were real. Plato tells us that the prisoners would begin with a 'game' of guessing as to which shadow would appear next. The prisoners who correctly guessed, would be praised by the others. They would call him as clever and best amongst them and say that he was a master of the nature who knew everything. Further Plato tells us what happens when one of the prisoners manages to leave the cave by escaping from their bindings. According to Plato he is shocked to see the real world. He is puzzled on discovering what is outside the cave and does not believe that whatever he has seen and witnessed can be real. However, with the passing time he becomes used to his new surroundings, he realizes that his former view of reality which he had made inside the cave on the basis of the shadows cast on the wall, was all wrong. He gradually begins to understand his new world, and realizes that the Sun is the only major source of the life and begins his intellectual journey where he discovers the real nature. He tries to understand its beauty and meaning. He realizes that his former life was not at all good in comparison to the present life where he has gained knowledge about the reality of life. He also understands that the guessing game which he played when he was in cave was useless.

This enlightenment urges him to return to the cave and to inform the other prisoners of his new findings and the knowledge of reality which he has gained from the free and shackle free nature outside the cave. However, the prisoners inside the cave were absolutely ignorant about the real world and therefore they did not believe him and instead of grateful they on the contrary threatened to kill him if he tries to set them free.

Interpretation of the Plato's Allegory of the Cave in the context of the present day world

Plato in the allegory of the cave tells us that most of the time, most of us live in

ignorance. He believes that the worst part of this situation, is that we do not even know that we are ignorant. Plato tells us to correlate our ordinary life, to the life of the prisoners in the cave. He further tells us that we are the prisoners, who live in the world of assumptions and false beliefs. We rely only on our senses to tell us about the reality, we neither take efforts to understand the real situation nor do we try to gain true knowledge. We blindly assume that only what our five senses tell us, is real.

Further it can be said that just like the prisoners, we all do the mistake of believing the ordinary world based only on our experience gained from our sense to be real. This leads to our acceptance of things at face value which is most of the times full of error. What Plato seems to be saying is that, even if the cave appears to be very enticing to the chained prisoners, however the truth is that it is not in their own interest. He tries to explain further that if the prisoner tries to stay in the cave, he will always be in a comfort zone and have lots of company of such people who always agree with him on the interpretations made by him about the shadows. As leaving the comfort zone is not an easy task and thus leaving the cave becomes equally difficult. However even if one of the prisoners' escapes and tries to go outside the cave, he first feels disoriented but with patience and perseverance, he gets his reward of seeing things as they really are and similarly we are just like the prisoners unaware of what is happening outside the prison premises and thus would feel equally disoriented when we try to step out of our comfort zone and think big. From the allegory of the cave we can say that for Plato the only one way to know reality is, relying on our reason rather than on our senses or our biased feelings because he says that reason is something that will never deceive us. Rather, it actually enables us to distinguish all that what is real from what is unreal. The philosophy behind Plato's Cave Allegory is relevant even in the present day, modern world in different capacities and circumstances. The allegory shows us how a common person like us who is brought up under a different narrow worldview, who is accustomed to a specific pattern of thinking and a specific way of life will find it difficult to accept another highly contrasting outlook and a different life. Such way of thinking and his worldview will make him rigid and he will resist and even reject the better possibility of change and progress. We are chained by our own faiths, beliefs, way of thinking, ideologies, influences, traditions, customs, habit, and so on. These

aspects not only impact individuals but also extend to institutions, politicians, administrative and the Government at large.

Conclusion and Suggestions

Plato has presented one of his best philosophies in his book *The Republic*. The seventh book of the *Republic* by Plato gives us the allegory of the cave and discusses the extent to which people should be educated and enlightened in society. Plato for the purpose of explaining this ideology has suggested that the king should carry out the role of enlightening the people in society and further suggested that the king should live a life of a philosopher and avoid committing any evil in the society. Plato utilized the idea of the philosopher king to explain his ideas of good governance backed by putting emphasis on education and justice. Plato in the allegory of the cave also explained about the analogy of the sun and the line. In the analogy of the cave he explained the living conditions of prisoners in the cave and through this he stated that the people should always avoid evil and be focused at doing good things in society. For this to be a reality the philosopher-king should be somebody who is a learned being having the interest of the majority at heart. The allegory of the cave in this regard illustrates the important role played by education on the human soul and on how crucial it is for a happy and content human life.

After analyzing the analogy of the cave Plato came up with his form of government. Plato stated that the best individuals in society should only always be allowed to rule for all the people. He believed that only well qualified persons should be eligible for occupying influential positions in the public and private sectors. Plato stated that the aristocracy is the best form of the government and whereas the democracy is the worst form of the government because it is the government by all and does not give the best individuals in society a chance to exercise their power. For Plato Democracy is like the tyranny because the majority people might push the leaders to implement such public policies which are against the interest of the masses. Plato in the allegory of the cave compared the Individuals who receive the best form of education to the Sun. Only because of the availability of the sun the prisoner from the cave saw real objects. Similarly, society and the people at large can achieve their goals, objectives and develop themselves by enhancing their qualities if the best and the most educated are allowed to rule. According to Plato, if this is

achieved then the justice would also be achieved for both the individual and the city.

Therefore, resting on Plato's ideology in the allegory of the cave we can suggest that the leaders and the politicians must be well educated and learned. They must be sensitive to the sufferings of the common people. They must always try to be responsive to the demands of the people at large. However, while doing so the leaders must apply their own knowledge, which they have gained from good quality higher education in order to analyze what is the best and what is the worst for the wellbeing of the society at large. The leaders should be the persons who have adequate education required for carrying out the good governance. Thus it can be finally concluded by saying that in the present day political system there should be the criteria of higher education as the required qualification for becoming the leader or the politician.

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